

Transfer Learning for Wall Temperature Prediction in Regeneratively Cooled 22N Thrust Chambers

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A neural network originally trained for hot gas wall temperature prediction in regeneratively cooled LOX/Methane rocket engines is adapted via transfer learning to predict hot gas wall temperatures in much smaller engines operated with nitrous oxide/ethane, which show different thermal behavior. The source net was trained with synthetic data generated by CFD simulations, whereas the transfer learning was done with a limited number of experimental data. The adapted network shows good prediction of the hot gas wall temperature in the test data set.

1 Introduction and Motivation

Hot gas wall temperature prediction is one of the main tasks in designing and optimizing a rocket engine. Complex and costly CFD simulations (computational fluid dynamics) or vague manual calculations based on Nusselt correlations are the standard way to estimate heat fluxes and wall temperatures [1]. Sophisticated CFD calculations achieve sufficient accuracy, but the associated high computational cost prevents an efficient integration in design-optimization loops. Surrogate models based on artificial neural networks (ANNs) provide substantial speed advantage. Dresia et al. show that an ANN, trained on data extracted from CFD simulations, is able to predict the wall temperature along rocket engine cooling channels using methane as coolant with convincing precision [2, 3]. This work deals with the question whether it is possible to adapt the ANN from Dresia et al. using transfer learning (TL) on the basis of real test data in a way that it can predict the heat transfer using another coolant - nitrous oxide (N_2O) - in a different engine with high prediction accuracy. It is investigated whether the ANN is able to be adapted to different coolants and geometries while retaining the underlying knowledge to heat transfer in general. Transfer learning is used in this case, as only a limited num-

ber of training data from experiments is available and no CFD simulations should be performed. The transfer learning approach is compared with training of an ANN from scratch.

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Source Model

As source model the trained ANN from Dresia et al. is used [2–4]. The ANN is able to predict hot gas wall temperatures for example along the cooling channels of the 25kN LUMEN rocket engine propelled with LOX/methane [5]. Training data was extracted from CFD simulations. The network architecture of this ANN used as source model is as follows: Four hidden layers, 408 neurons per hidden layer. The mean absolute error (MAE) of the wall temperature prediction was 8.40 K on the validation set with standard deviation of 18.5 K [2–4].

2.2 Transfer Learning

The term "transfer learning" describes a field in machine learning in which a pre-trained model is re-used on a new or different problem. The underlying data-distribution (domain) of two training data sets is different [6]. This can be given with regard to the features X , the labels Y or the predictions $P(Y|X)$ [7]. What was previously learned from a source data set should be transferred to a changed environment and thus used again. The aim of transfer learning is to create a model that can infer the distribution of a target T based on the distribution of data from a source S [8]. This task arises from the problem that (labeled) data in the target domain is often difficult or impossible to record and/or generating it is associated with high financial or time costs [9]. As a result, there is often only a small number of target data points available. The situation is different in the source domain,

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where a large amount of data e.g. from physical models - such as the aforementioned CFD simulations - is already available. This is the case for the heat transfer prediction in nitrous oxide thrusters: A large amount of source data from engines operated with methane is available from CFD, while there is only limited experimental data from the nitrous oxide thrusters. The basic assumption of transfer learning is that the learned relationship P_S of the source model can be transferred to the target model and ensure improved prediction results there - in comparison to training the model from scratch using only the target data set. However, this only works well if both distributions are approximately the same ($P_S \approx P_T$) [6, 9].

3 Data Preparation

3.1 Data Generation

IDENO-22 HyNOx engines using ethane and nitrous oxide developed at DLR and ISP-Tech are used to generate the training data [10]. These are regeneratively cooled orbital propulsion thrusters in the 22N thrust class. Additively manufactured stainless steel is used to produce the thrusters. Three different prototypes (IDENO-22B1, IDENO-22C and HyNOx-22A) are used in this work [10], all of which are operated under atmospheric conditions at test bench M11.5 in Lampoldshausen [11]. The prototypes differ in cooling channel and injection geometries and therefore provide variations in geometrical data used as input.

3.2 Processing into Training Data

Not all experiments performed with the IDENO-22 thrusters are suitable for processing into training data for the ANN. As the ANN should predict steady state temperatures, only those trials that are considered long-term test with experiment duration $> 10s$ and for which successful ignition was recorded are used. This results in 90 tests, each of which is manually checked if thermal steady state is reached. The data recorded during the experiments and relevant for this work include: Pressure at the cooling channel inlet - P_{CCin} (in bar), mass flow of the nitrous oxide - \dot{m}_{N_2O} (in g/s) and temperatures at the cooling channel inlet and outlet - T_{CCin} and T_{CCout} (each in °C) and at three positions on the combustion chamber wall - T_{C01} , T_{C02} and T_{C03} (each in °C). As, in comparison to the CFD simulation, no continuous measurement of the data along the cooling channel is available, the thruster is divided in three sections, corresponding to the thermocouple measurement positions. At these three positions input data is calculated from the measured

values. All needed input variables can be calculated from measured data and the respective geometries of the engines. The input vector variables are exactly the same as described in the paper from Dresia et al. [3] as the architecture of the NN is not changed. One averaged data point per second of the experiment is used as input value. The input vector of the ANN and the way the values are extracted from the measured or geometric variables is summarized in table 1. The train-

	Variable	calculated/measured from
j_m	massflow density	calculated from massflow and cooling channel area
r	wall roughness	estimated from manufacturer data
\dot{q}	heatflux density	Calculated from coolant temperature difference and wall surface area
h	coolant ethalpy	Calculated using refprop [12] and coolant temperature
p	coolant pressure	Calculated using measured inflow pressure and pressure drop calculation from Darcy-Weisbach [13]
A	Cooling channel area	Taken from CAD model
AR	Cooling channel aspect ratio	Taken from CAD model
d	Wall thickness	Taken from CAD model
κ	Cooling channel curvature	Taken from CAD model
z	Flow length	Taken from CAD model
d_{Fin}	Fin thickness	Taken from CAD model

Table 1: Input Vector and source of the data

ing data set is split into training and validation data in a ratio of 95:5 - whereby the split was retained from the previous work by Dresia et al. [3]. Data from any of the three engine models is taken randomly from the resulting ≈ 6.500 data points. The training, validation and test sets are then scaled using the standard scaler, which is fitted using the training set [14].

4 Algorithm Selection

The Awesome Domain Adaptation Python Toolbox (ADAPT) library [15] is used, which provides implementations for various TL and DA algorithms. ADAPT is open source, compatible with both Scikit-Learn [16] and TensorFlow [17] and offers extensive documentation. In the context of this work, no access to source

data from the original training is assumed, but the trained source ANN is available. The training data and labels used for the transfer learning are available. With these requirements two algorithms implemented in ADAPT come into account [15]: Regular-TransferNN (RTNN) and FineTuning (FT). The FT algorithm is particularly suitable for the TL of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), which are often used for image classification. As this is not the case in this work, FT is not used. The applied RTNN algorithm, on the other hand, directly adapts the parameters of the source ANN using the labeled target data by means of a target function that is regularized by the Euclidean distance between the source and received target parameters [18]:

$$\beta_T = \underset{\beta=(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_D)}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\| f(x_T, \beta) - y_T \right\|^2 + \sum_{i=1}^D \lambda_i \left\| \beta_i - \beta_{Si} \right\|^2 \quad (1)$$

where β_S and β_T are the parameters of the source and target ANN. β are the parameters of the ANN f to be optimized with D layers. λ_i is the regularizing parameter of layer i defining how much the weights of the source net are adapted.

5 Hyperparameter Determination

The number of training epochs as well as the value of the regularization parameter λ is optimized. Training takes about one second per epoch on an Intel® Core™ i5-8500 processor. The predictive power of the ANN when evaluated at the validation data set improves up to the 600 training epochs, whereas it deteriorates again with longer training - which is an indicator for overfitting from an epoch number > 600 . 535 training epochs are selected as this achieves the best prediction. The choice of $\lambda = 0.5$ reduces the mean squared error MSE by 1/3 and the maximum squared error MaxSE by up to 2/3 compared to the standard value and is therefore retained. As a result, the adapted ANN predicts the wall temperatures of the test data set with an average deviation of 5.63 K and a maximum deviation of 14.99 K. For the regularization, the choice of $\lambda = 0.5$ means that the adaptation of the parameters of the source ANN is reduced.

6 Results and Discussion

The wall temperature predictions of the adapted TL-ANN, which was trained with regularization $\lambda = 0.5$ and 535 epochs is analyzed below using the (unseen) test data set. Figure 1 shows in the upper part for

each section of the combustion chamber the predicted wall temperature (in orange) and the corresponding measured value (in blue). The values are rounded per second and one test of 8 second duration is shown. In the lower part, the errors (MSE, MAE and mean absolute percentage error MAPE) together with the standard deviation of the respective section for both tests of the test data set can be seen. The TL-ANN has managed to predict the wall temperature accurately in each section of the previously unknown test data. Furthermore, the errors per section are roughly comparable across both trials of the test data set - the MAE is consistently below 10 K. This result is a hint that there is no "overfitting on training data", as the TL-ANN is able to successfully predict the unknown test data. Without further experimental or simulation data, that also adequately covers larger datasets it is not possible to make qualitative statements about the general prediction accuracy of the TL-ANN apart from the previously used operating points of the HyNOx engines. Comparison with the prediction of the source net show, that the original NN was not able to predict the temperatures for the nitrous oxide case correctly.

6.1 Comparison with Fine Tuning and Training from Scratch

For comparing the used method of transfer learning with other approaches, also a network trained from scratch (SCR) is created. The SCR method predicts the test data per section with a maximum MAE of around 20 K. The predictions of the TL method, which achieves a maximum MAE of around 10 K is slightly better. Nevertheless, these differences are rather marginal for real-world applicability. Heat maps offer the possibility to identify problems of a ANN with regard to overfitting. Figures 2 and 3 show the predicted wall temperatures of artificially generated input data sets in one heat map each for transfer learning and training from scratch. As input the variables shown on the axis are varied in the given range (around the mean value of the training data set) and the other input variables are kept constant. Figure 3 shows that the TL-ANN predicts a reduced wall temperature for an increasing cooling mass flux density which is physically rational. The peak of the wall temperature visible on the far left in the range of the heat flux density of approx. 1 to 1.5 MW/m² initially seems nonphysical, as increasing heat flux input would also result in increasing wall temperatures. However, this could be an artefact of the Source-ANN. When methane is used as a coolant, heat transfer deterioration (HTD) is observed near the critical point for low mass flows [3]. Waxenegger-Wilfing et al have shown that the effect of HTD with methane is both

Figure 1: Prediction error in test data.

Figure 2: Heatmap of the NN trained from scratch

Figure 3: Heatmap of the NN used in this work, trained with transfer learning

represented in the generated CFD simulation data and learnt from the source ANN [4]. The choice of regularization with $\lambda = 0.5$ could make the occurrence of such an artifact quite plausible, especially since only very few real training data points fall within the range of the mass flux density of around $800\text{kg}/\text{sm}^2$. The

peak previously described does not appear at all in the heatmap (Fig. 2) created with the ANN trained from scratch. This reinforces the assumption that this could be the HTD effect learnt from the source ANN. In the heat map showing the training from scratch results, there is a slight discontinuity in the center of the image at the heat flux density of $1.56\text{MW}/\text{m}^2$ and $1.91\text{MW}/\text{m}^2$, which extends over the entire range of the mass flux density shown in the heat map. This area contains particularly large number of training data points in this range. This could be an indication of overfitting of the ANN trained only from scratch without transfer-learning.

To exclude overfitting further investigation of the model will be needed. Three approaches are possible: First, generate new, unseen test data and check the prediction of the model. Further, the predictions can be cross checked with the predictions given from special nusselt correlations [1], however these correlations also tend to be not very precise. And thirdly, the prediction could be compared with the result of CFD simulationsm of the experiment. Before further usage of the model as prediction tool, at least one of this options should be applied. The current database does not allow for more extensive investigations with regard to overfitting, due to the sparse number of data points.

7 Conclusion and Outlook

It was shown that transfer learning approaches can be used to adapt an already existing ANN for heat

transfer prediction with a specific propellant, in this case methane/LOX, to predict wall temperatures in rocket engines using other propellants, in this case nitrous oxide/ethane. Only a limited number of experimental training data was sufficient to achieve satisfying prediction results with the model. However for a complete exclusion of overfitting and validation in a wide application area, a larger test data set would be needed. The transfer learning net performed better than a net trained from scratch. In the future this method should be tested with a wider database of experimental data. Furthermore, the ANN could be adapted to more propellants. Also a universal wall temperature prediction tool could be generated if the propellant serves as input variable as well.

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